

Impact of the Operation of a Standing Column Well on Clogging and Scaling

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Abstract

A Standing Column Well (SCW) is a low-temperature geothermal system that shows a great potential to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. In a SCW, groundwater is continuously recirculated in an uncased well, bringing the water in direct contact with the rock. Since the physico-chemistry of groundwater is modified by the operation, this new equilibrium can be prone to clogging. The work achieved so far shows a direct link between the operation of a SCW and the load of calcium. Our results indicate that on/off submersible pump sequences create ideal conditions for precipitation in geothermal equipments, such as heat exchangers.

1. Introduction

SCWs demonstrate high heat exchange rate (Orio et al. 2005) and represent a promising solution among the available ground heat exchangers. It can reduce the capital cost compared to closed-loop systems (Lee 2009; O'Neil et al. 2006). SCWs can be installed in small areas such as dense urban zones (Pasquier et al. 2016). In a SCW, groundwater is continuously recirculated in an uncased well, bringing the water in direct contact with the rock. Since groundwater is being mixed, oxygenated, and warmed or cooled, the well and the mechanical equipments can be prone to clogging and scaling (Rafferty 2004), which can impact the long-term performance and maintenance costs of the system. More specifically, calcium carbonate scaling and iron-related fouling are the most common water quality problems (Rafferty 2004; Park et al. 2015). In the Montreal area, the substratum is composed of carbonate sedimentary rocks, which can lead to calcium carbonate precipitation during SCW operation. Although current literature identifies the main causes of clogging, the impact of the operation strategy of a SCW has yet not been investigated.

2. Methods and techniques

The chemical signature of groundwater and the operation parameters of an experimental SCW were monitored during a one-year period through the use of a geothermal mobile unit. This unit contains four heat pumps, a heat exchanger, monitoring devices and a

water treatment unit that can treat a fraction of the total flow.

3. Results

The work achieved so far shows a direct link between the operation of a SCW and the concentration of calcium in groundwater. More specifically, our results indicate that on/off sequences create ideal conditions for increase of calcium content in the groundwater. After two years of operation and 13 involuntary on/off sequences, two flow sensors were cleaned (Fig. 1). This operation has permitted to sample the deposit on the pipe. It was analyzed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The results show that this deposit is higher concentrated in calcium, oxygen and carbon than other chemical elements.

Fig. 1 Picture of a flow meter, where it is possible to observe depositions after two years of operation.

4. Discussion

Our observations showed that on/off sequences create ideal conditions for groundwater to dissolve the rock, i.e. increase the geochemical load. The direct consequence of this observation is the potential precipitation in mechanical equipments. Indeed, the temperature increase generated by equilibrium with the warm laboratory as well as water stagnation creates optimal conditions for calcite precipitation.

5. Conclusions

The study has demonstrated the impact of the operation of a SCW that can lead to the precipitation of a thin layer of calcium carbonates. Nevertheless, after two years of operation, the effect of precipitation is limited to a couple of monitoring devices (i.e. flow meters) and do not affect the entire system.

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